

Data Availability Statement

The data used for this project is available through the California Digital Library's "Merritt" data repository.

We have deposited three sets of data in the repository which can be used in conjunction with our code, available as noted in the article from Source Forge.

The three datasets, and their DOI (xxxx), are as follows:

- (a) the concatenated dictionary file, stored as a json (dictionary_20140605.json)
- (b) the untagged and tagged Fornaldarsögur corpus (allvol.zip and icemorph_corpus-2014-06-01.zip)
- (c) the EXPERT and GOLD training/testing corpora (tagged_corpora_20140605.json)